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A Structural Analysis of the Denarii of
Coelius Caldus (*RRC* 437)

by

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[PLATES 18-19]

“Ricca di recondite notizie è la medaglia,
di cui imprendo a parlare nella presente osservazione,
della quale niuno a mio giudizio ha finora compreso
il vero significato. Appartiene alla gente Celia...”

Bartolomeo Borghesi²

THE LATE Republican denarii signed by CALDVS IIIVIR were minted by C. Coelius Calvus, well known as the quaestor of Cilicia in 50 BC³ from the correspondence of Cicero, who made a deprecatory remark about the young man in one of the pertinent letters.⁴ Calvus must have held office as a moneyer in 53, 52 or 51 BC, with one of the latter two years perhaps being more likely.⁵ The coins struck in his name are famous for two reasons which are interconnected. Firstly, they are among the prime examples of Republican denarii literally overstuffed with references to the family history of the moneyer, encompassing not only the main images of obverse and reverse of each variety of Calvus' coins, but also the legends, which are in part highly abbreviated, as well as a host of additional symbols in the left and right fields

¹ Anna Zawadzka studied the representations of Gauls on Roman Republican coinage at the 2006 Graduate Seminar of the American Numismatic Society and the overview of Gallic attributes in the present article is based on the seminar paper submitted to the ANS in February 2007. Over the past years, her research on the Romans and Barbarians has been sponsored by the Fulbright Commission, the Polish Ministry of Science and Higher Education, the Lanckoroński Foundation and the Italian Ministry of Foreign Affairs. Her work on this article was financed by the National Science Centre Poland, decision no. DEC-2013/09/N/HS3/02199, and the Austrian Academy of Sciences.

² *Œuvres complètes de Bartolomeo Borghesi*, vols 1 and 2: *Œuvres numismatiques* (Paris, 1862–4), vol. 1, p. 319 (Decade VI, Osservazione IX).

³ T.R.S. Broughton, *The Magistrates of the Roman Republic* [= *MRR*], 3 vols (New York, 1951–1952 [vols 1 and 2], Atlanta/Georgia, 1986 [vol. 3 = Supplement]), vol. 2, p. 250. F. Münzer, article ‘Coelius no. 14’, *RE* 4.1 (1900), col. 196.

⁴ Cic. Att. 6.6.3: *Nos provinciae praefecimus Coelium. ‘Puerum’ inquires ‘et fortasse fatuum et non gravem et non continentem!’ Adsentior; fieri non potuit aliter.*

⁵ For a discussion of the date of the issue, see B. Woytek, *Arma et nummi. Forschungen zur römischen Finanzgeschichte und Münzprägung der Jahre 49–42 v. Chr.* (Vienna, 2003), pp. 89f. (with the bibliography up to 2003). In *RRC*, the issue was assigned to 51 BC (p. 457); see also W. Hollstein, *Die stadtrömische Münzprägung der Jahre 78–50 v. Chr. zwischen politischer Aktualität und Familienthematik. Kommentar und Bibliographie.* Quellen und Forschungen zur Antiken Welt 14 (Munich, 1993; reprinted 2001), p. 382 (“ca. 51”).

of many of the obverse and reverse types. The second feature for which this denarius issue is celebrated is the obverse common to all of its varieties: the powerful portrait of the pride of the family, the moneyer's grandfather C. Coelius Calvus, a *homo novus*, consul of 94 BC,⁶ whose head is so typical that it is hardly possible to imagine any overview of Late Republican portrait art without it.⁷

Despite almost countless attempts to come to grips with the difficult typology of the coins of Coelius Calvus, considerable uncertainties of interpretation persist, and contradictions in the bibliography abound. We believe that a fresh look at the types, the legends and the structure of the issue, on the basis of current historical and numismatic scholarship, makes it clear that some of the explanations hitherto advanced may safely be dismissed, since they were triggered by misunderstandings of certain elements of the iconography. In our opinion, the key to a correct interpretation of the varieties of the coins lies in analysing them not just one by one, but in considering the issue as a whole. In doing so, we hope to demonstrate that many current interpretations of *RRC* 437 represent a clear infringement of the so-called *lex parsimoniae*, a problem-solving principle commonly attributed to the Scholastic philosopher William of Ockham (c.1287–1347), according to which *pluralitas non est ponenda sine necessitate*, or *entia non sunt multiplicanda praeter necessitatem*: “entities must not be multiplied beyond necessity”.

The issue of Calvus comprises two main types of roughly the same size,⁸ for each of which there are two or more varieties. While one main type couples the portrait of the consul of 94 BC, invariably identified as C. COEL. CALDVS COS in the obverse legend,⁹ with a radiate head of Sol on the reverse (*RRC* 437/1a–b; **pl. 18, fig. 1**), the other main type associates the portrait with a more unusual depiction: a togate man, his head covered, who is preparing an *epulum* on a structure resembling an altar behind which he is standing (*RRC* 437/2–4; **pls 18–19, figs 2–5**). The front of the ‘altar’ (decorated with volutes on the top) is inscribed with the priest’s name and title, the fullest version of which is L. CALDVS / VIIVIR EPVL(onum). This man seems to be the moneyer’s father, since we know from Cicero’s letter fam. 2.19.1 that the full name of its addressee, the quaestor of 50 BC, was C. Coelius L.f. C.n. Calvus. Hence, on the denarii *RRC* 437/2–4 both the father and the grandfather of the then *monetalis* are represented. The moneyer’s signature CALDVS IIIIVIR is

⁶F. Münzer, article ‘Coelius no. 12’, *RE* 4.1 (1900), cols 195–6. He was presumably responsible for the production of the denarius issue *RRC* 318 (dated to 104 BC by Michael Crawford in *RRC*).

⁷See for example J.M.C. Toynbee, *Roman Historical Portraits* (Ithaca, NY, 1978), p. 21; G. Lahusen, *Die Bildnismünzen der römischen Republik* (Munich, 1989), pp. 47–50; G. Lahusen, *Römische Bildnisse. Auftraggeber – Funktionen – Standorte* (Darmstadt, 2010), pp. 213f. M.-L. Vollenweider, *Die Porträtgemmen der römischen Republik*, 2 vols (Mainz am Rhein, 1972–4), pp. 31f. and pls 22–4, likens the portrait of L. Coelius Calvus on these coins to the head on a carnelian in the Florence collection. However, it remains unclear if the same individual is depicted.

⁸Crawford estimated 33 obverse dies for each type (*RRC* p. 458), and an approximately equal distribution of the denarii *RRC* 437 over these two types is reflected in the material known to us.

⁹The element COS is always separated from the rest of the legend and placed beneath the truncation of the head. Hence, the C. COEL. CALDVS came to have a double meaning, since the moneyer responsible for the issue and his grandfather (depicted on the obverse and described by the legend) were homonymous.

always placed on the reverse of the coins: it follows the circumference of the denarii in the right field on *RRC* 437/1, and is to be read in the exergue of *RRC* 437/2–4, where, for reasons of space, the ALD of the name is in ligature. The one attribute accompanying the consul's portrait head on the variety *RRC* 437/1a–b is a tablet (*tabella*) inscribed with the two letters L and D in the left obverse field. It recalls the *lex Coelia tabellaria* of 107 BC, which was introduced by C. Coelius Caldus (cos. 94) in his tribunate; through this law the use of *tabellae* was instituted also for trials for high treason.¹⁰ The two letters on the wooden tablet stand for *l(ibero)* and *d(amno)*; apparently voters were supposed to strike out one of the options during the vote.

So far, so good. But “from here we set sail on a sea of confusion”, as one of the more recent commentators of the series aptly remarked.¹¹ Problems start with the reverses of the second main type (*RRC* 437/2–4), which make it evident that, apart from the political, especially legislative activity of C. Coelius Caldus (cos. 94), and the religious office of L. Coelius Caldus, the military glory of at least one of the moneyer's ancestors was an important point he wanted to celebrate. The ‘altar’ at which the *VIIvir epulonum* L. Coelius Caldus is preparing the ritual meal on *RRC* 437/2–4 is flanked by two trophies. The two trophies are unmistakably differentiated from one another by the types of foreign military equipment with which they are decorated.¹² These trophies are accompanied by one vertical legend each, reading C. CALDVS and IMP A (or a ligature of AV or AN) X.

One of the two trophies is clearly intended to commemorate a victory over Gauls: it invariably features an oblong shield (with a central boss, a long vertical spine, and four S-shaped elements), a helmet with two horns and a central ‘spike’ or decoration, a (sometimes long) sword on a sword-belt as well as a *carnyx* and a spear (or javelin). The other trophy looks completely different: it comprises a round shield, a helmet of another type with a plume, a short sword at the belt and two elongated objects (either javelins or spears), either crossed or parallel to one another.

On the vast majority of the denarii of Caldus, the Gallic trophy is to the right of the ‘altar’ (*RRC* 437/2a, 3a, 4a: **pl. 18, figs 2–4**), but in exceptional cases the two *tropaea* change sides (*RRC* 437/2b, 3b and 4b: **pl. 19, fig. 5**); also, there are smaller iconographic differences between various dies such as whether the shields are mounted on the outside (this is the usual variety) or on the inside of the trophy. Michael Crawford has correctly observed that the accompanying legends C. CALDVS and IMP A (or a ligature of AV or AN) X are aligned to the position of the trophies: the somewhat mysterious, highly abbreviated IMP-legend is always to be found next to the Gallic trophy. However, perhaps one should not accept his suggestion that this part of the inscription may be associated exclusively with the Gallic *tropaeum*, and not the other one. The relevant coins come from a very small number of reverse dies, and in view of the fact that their inscription IMP A (or AV/AN) X / C. CALDVS is

¹⁰ Münzer, ‘Coelius no. 12’ (n. 6 above), col. 196 (with reference to the literary sources).

¹¹ M. Harlan, *Roman Republican Moneyers and their Coins 63 BC–49 BC* (London, 1995), p. 161.

¹² The general appearance of this reverse image is somewhat reminiscent of the Julio-Claudian bronzes from Lugdunum, featuring the altar of Roma and Augustus on the reverse, which is flanked by two columns with statues of Victory on them: see *RIC* I² Augustus 229ff.

structurally quite abnormal, as compared to the usual form, the natural explanation seems to be that an engraver mistakenly transposed the position of the trophies (plus the accompanying legends) on a few dies.

The four main questions which gave rise to disagreement in recent scholarship regarding the denarii of Calvus of the late fifties are the following: (i) Against which foreign peoples were the military victories evoked by the imagery on the denarii won? (ii) What is the significance of the head of Sol on the reverse of the sub-type *RRC* 437/1 – does it have a geographical connotation here? And what does the letter S, to be read in the left field of the variety *RRC* 437/1b next to the head of Sol, stand for? (iii) What is the correct interpretation of the highly abbreviated vertical reverse legends on *RRC* 437/2–4? (iv) What is the precise meaning (if any) of the reverse type of these coins, juxtaposing the *epulum* and military trophies?

Before we proceed to an examination of these questions, a general point. In view of the more than 400-year-long history of scholarship on the issue of Calvus, it would be futile to try and provide a thorough survey of research in the present context, especially since we are fortunate to have two recent contributions containing relatively exhaustive bibliographical references. In the relevant chapter of his 1993 monograph, Wilhelm Hollstein covers a good deal of the literature from the end of the 19th century to the late 1980s or early 90s.¹³ In 1998, Ernst Badian published an important paper on this issue, in which he quite systematically cited interpretations of the type given by the ‘Old Masters’ of our discipline, from Fulvio Orsini (1529–1600) onward. Badian’s article was the reaction – at times somewhat grumpy in tone – of a senior classical scholar, who was also an avid collector of Roman Republican coins, by the way,¹⁴ to the treatment of this issue by Michael Harlan (above, n. 11), which was primarily aimed at an audience of laymen lacking scholarly training, and was perceived to be inadequate by Badian. Unfortunately, Badian himself was unaware of Hollstein’s work on the denarii of Calvus, which is much more scholarly and, in many aspects, better informed than Harlan’s. Also, the fact that Badian chose to publish the article in a non-numismatic journal, under a very general title which carefully avoided any indication as to which coins he was dealing with,¹⁵ did not help with the reception of his work among numismatists. However, in what follows we will mainly focus on the primary material, and on the literature published after Badian. We shall start with the core of our argument.

The imagery of *RRC* 437: types and symbols referring to military victories

Among the numerous varieties of the two main denarius types of Calvus, one may distinguish four obverse or reverse types, on each of which two attributes (or sets of attributes) denoting the ethnicity of defeated peoples are illustrated.

¹³ Hollstein, *Die stadtrömische Münzprägung* (n. 5 above), pp. 361–9.

¹⁴ In 2001, Badian donated his collection of more than 1200 Republican specimens to the “Special Collections and Archives Department” of the Rutgers University Libraries, New Jersey. It is now available online: <<http://www.libraries.rutgers.edu/rul/projects/romancoins/>> [accessed on 30 December 2015].

¹⁵ E. Badian, ‘Two numismatic phantoms. The false priest and the spurious son’, *Arctos* 32 (1998), pp. 45–60.

- A. oval shield – round shield: depicted behind and in front of the head of Sol respectively (RRC 437/1a–b, reverse). **Pl. 18, fig. 1.**
- B. *vexillum* inscribed HIS – boar standard: depicted behind and in front of the portrait of Calvus respectively (RRC 437/2a–b, 3a–b, obverse).¹⁶ **Pl. 18, figs 2–3.**
- C. *carnyx* and spear – *vexillum* inscribed HIS: depicted behind and in front of the portrait of Calvus respectively (RRC 437/4a–b obverse).¹⁷ **Pls 18–19, figs 4–5.**
- D. Gallic trophy with oval shield, horned helmet, *carnyx* etc. – trophy with round shield: placed to the left and to the right of the altar-like structure at which the *Vilvir epulonum* L. Coelius Calvus is depicted (RRC 437/2a–b, 3a–b, 4a–b, reverse).¹⁸ **Pls 18–19, figs 2–5.**

The one literary testimony of the military activity of C. Coelius Calvus, cos. 94 BC, in the provinces is Liv. per. 73: *C. Coelius in Gallia transalpina Salluvios rebellantes vicit* (90 BC).¹⁹ For this reason, the unmistakably Gallic trophy of our type D above is universally – and doubtless correctly – taken to refer to Calvus' victory over the Salluvii,²⁰ and starting from this observation a general consensus has emerged in scholarship that several of the objects featured on types A–C allude to this military success: namely the oval shield on A, the standard in the form of a boar on B, and the *carnyx* and spear on type C. In fact, there is a strong probability that the designers or die-cutters responsible for the issue also included a special hint at the Salluvii on RRC 437/1b: as mentioned above, on this variety the letter S appears in the left

¹⁶ Within our type B, there are two subtypes, differing only in the respective position of the attributes: on RRC 437/2a–b, the standard inscribed HIS is in the left and the boar standard in the right field; on the very rare varieties RRC 437/3a–b the position of the standards is reversed.

¹⁷ We know virtually no specimens of this sub-type (the rarest one), on which all the elements of the design are clearly in evidence; normally either the *carnyx* or the *vexillum* are partly or completely off the flan.

¹⁸ Within our type D, there are two subtypes, which differ only in the respective position of the trophies, as already discussed above in the text.

¹⁹ Hence, Calvus was campaigning in Transalpine Gaul after his consulship.

²⁰ In the ancient written sources, Salluvii (or *Salyes* in Greek) are initially labelled as “Ligurians”, then as “Celtoligurians”, “Celts” or “Gauls”. For references, see J.B. Keune, article ‘Salluvi’, *RE* 1A.2 (1920), cols 1970–5, at 1970–1. The Roman sources contemporary to the conquest of their region, or preserving contemporary information, still call them “Ligurians”: cf. the triumphs *de Liguribus Vocontieis Salluveisq(ue)* mentioned under the years 123 and 122 BC in the *Fasti Triumphales*. Livy, on the other hand, when writing about the campaigns of M. Fulvius Flaccus in 125–4 BC, called them “Galli” (Liv. per. 60: *M. Fulvius Flaccus [...] missus in auxilium Massiliensium adversus Salluvios Gallos, qui fines Massiliensium populabantur*). Of course, in the chronological context of Caesar's conquest of Gaul, when the issue of C. Coelius Calvus was struck, the moneyer presented the victory of his ancestor as a Gallic victory. For a recent overview of theories and a comprehensive bibliography on the complex question of the relation between “Celtic” and “Ligurian” in this region, see S. Collin Bouffier and D. Garcia, ‘Greeks, Celts and Ligurians in South-East Gaul: ethnicity and archaeology’, in: A. Hermay and G. R. Tsetskhladze (eds), *From the Pillars of Hercules to the Footsteps of the Argonauts*. *Colloquia Antiqua* 4 (Leuven – Paris – Walpole, MA, 2012), pp. 21–36.

field of the reverse, above the oval shield and behind the head of Sol (**Pl. 18, fig. 1**). Despite the fact that nearly all modern commentators, including Borghesi, Crawford and Badian, took the S to stand for S(ol),²¹ the expansion S(alluvii), proposed by Wilhelm Hollstein is much to be preferred. Sol, with his radiate crown, did not need an identification; perhaps the L – presumably standing for L(ycia) – appearing next to a military trophy on the aurei *RRC* 507/1b struck by Casca Longus for Brutus provides a parallel to the S on our coins.²²

Let us briefly discuss the Gallic attributes featured on these coins. The *carnyx* (on types C and D), a Celtic (war-)trumpet with a bell in the shape of boar's open mouth, is one of the most frequent attributes evoking victories over the Gauls on Roman Republican coinage. It is often part of (or accompanies) Gallic trophies, as for example on the reverses of quinarii commemorating Marius' defeat of the Cimbri and Teutones²³ and on the coinage celebrating Caesar's conquest of Gaul,²⁴ but it also appears on its own as a symbol of Gaul in general or Gallic victory in particular. This is the case on denarii of the moneyer D. Iunius Silanus,²⁵ and on coins struck by Caesarian moneyers of 48 BC: the obverse of Hostilius Saserna's famous denarii with the *carnyx* behind the head of a Gallic captive woman (*RRC* 448/3), and the reverse of denarii of Decimus Brutus Albinus, featuring two crossed *carnyces* as the main motif (*RRC* 450/1).²⁶ It should be superfluous to remark, in this context, that on Caesar's denarii *RRC* 443 the elephant of course does not trample a *carnyx*,²⁷ but we mention it here, since old myths often die hard, especially in numismatics.

²¹ Cp. Borghesi, *Œuvres numismatiques* (n. 2 above), vol. 1, p. 320; Crawford, *RRC* p. 458, n. 1 (without discussion); Badian, 'Two numismatic phantoms' (n. 15 above), p. 48, n. 4: "That the letter S should be used (or needed) to identify Sol seems an unpalatable idea, but may well be correct". Badian went on to speculate that "it got on to the dies through an engraver's mistake, possibly from a note on his instructions calling for a head of Sol".

²² See Hollstein, *Die stadtrömische Münzprägung* (n. 5 above), p. 366, as well as the article by Hollstein in this volume.

²³ *RRC* 326/2 and 332/1. The invasion of the Cimbri and Teutones of course involved both Germanic and Celtic tribes, but all of them were initially labelled as *Galli* by the Romans, for whom the war counted among the *bella Gallica*.

²⁴ *RRC* 448/1, 452/1–2, 452/4–5, 468/1–2, 482/1. The latter coin type is of uncertain attribution and production date: see Woytek, *Arma et nummi* (n. 5 above), p. 467–72.

²⁵ *RRC* 337/1 (dated to 91 BC by Crawford), where a *carnyx* lies under the *biga* driven by Victory.

²⁶ For an interim index of representations of the *carnyx* on Roman coinage and in ancient art in general (listing, besides coins, 44 monuments with *carnyces*) see F. Hunter, 'The Carnyx in Iron Age Europe', *Antiquaries Journal* 81 (2001), pp. 77–108, at 92 and 101–2 (this includes, however, also Dacian *carnyces* and other attestations from imperial times which may denote victories not over Celts, but over other peoples). See also A. Zawadzka, 'Some Gallic attributes on Roman Republican coins in the light of recent archaeological findings', paper submitted for the *Proceedings of the XVth International Numismatic Congress, Taormina*, 21–26 September 2015. For indigenous numismatic representations, see in particular F. Hunter, 'The carnyx and other trumpets on Celtic coins', in: J. van Heesch and I. Heeren (eds), *Coinage in the Iron Age: Essays in Honour of Simone Scheers* (London, 2009), pp. 231–48. For the most recent overview of archaeological finds of Gallic *carnyces*, see A. Zawadzka, 'A preliminary report of a study of the *carnyx* from Abentheuer', *Światowit* [2016] (in press). The publication of a Ph.D. thesis on the *carnyx* by F. Hunter is in preparation.

²⁷ See Woytek, *Arma et nummi* (note 5 above, pp. 122f.); D. Woods, 'Caesar the Elephant against Juba the Snake', *NC* 169 (2009), pp. 189–92 acknowledges this, but still overinterprets the obverse type.

The characteristic combination of a *carnyx* and an impressive spear with a large leaf-shaped spearhead – as on our type C – also appears on another Roman Republican denarius issue: in the hands of a naked Gallic charioteer on the reverse of *denarii serrati* struck at the Roman colony of Narbo (RRC 282; **pl. 19, fig. 6**). The warrior was traditionally thought to be the Arvernian king Bituitus,²⁸ but one of the present authors concurs with other researchers in believing that this identification is not advisable.²⁹ In any case, both coin types refer to southern Gaul, and despite Badian's claim to the contrary,³⁰ the spear on the denarii of Caldus may have some local significance; it might represent a *gaesum* (probably a javelin),³¹ the Gallic pole weapon *par excellence* in the eyes of the Romans,³² to whom it was known by its Celtic name.³³ The tribe of the Salluvii defeated by C. Coelius Caldus inhabited the territory between the Rhone and the Alps,³⁴ from where, according to Polybius, Gallic mercenaries called *Gaesati* had been recruited by the North Italian Gauls for the wars they waged against the Romans at the end of the third century BC.³⁵

The oval shield (with a central rib) of the *scutum* (*thyreós*) type which is depicted on our iconographic types A and D is one of the most common Gallic attributes in ancient art in general³⁶ and on Roman Republican coinage in particular, its popularity even exceeding that of the *carnyx* as a motif. Such an oval shield appears,

²⁸ See RRC, p. 299 for references.

²⁹ See recently B. Woytek, 'Der Fremde im Münzbild. Zur Herausbildung ikonographischer Konventionen der Darstellung von Barbaren in der römischen Münzprägung', in: A. Pülz and E. Trinkl (eds), *Das Eigene und das Fremde. Tagung des Zentrums Archäologie und Altertumswissenschaften an der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften, 26.–27. März 2012* (Vienna, 2015), pp. 105–22, at p. 109.

³⁰ Badian, 'Two numismatic phantoms' (n. 15 above), pp. 48f.

³¹ See Caes. Gall. 3.4.1; Prop. 4.10.42.

³² See Serv. Aen. 7.664: *pilum proprie est hasta Romana, ut gaesa Gallorum, sarissae Macedonum*; Non. 555.9 M. (= p. 891 L.): *Gaesa telum Galliarum tenerum*. Warriors often seem to have used a pair of these javelins, although this does not compromise the identification of the object on Caldus' coins: for *duo gaesa* or *bina gaesa* see Liv. 9.36.6, Verg. Aen. 8.661f. and Non. 555.11f. M. (= p. 891 L., from Varro, *de vita p. R.*, book 3).

³³ See O. Fiebiger, article 'Gaesum', *RE* 7.1 (1910), cols 463f.

³⁴ Strab. 4.1.11 (p. 185); for the sources see Keune, 'Salluvi' (n. 20 above), cols 1971f. For their territory in detail, see G. Barroul, *Les peuples préromains du Sud-Est de la Gaule. Étude de géographie historique* (Paris, 1969), pp. 187–230.

³⁵ See esp. Polyb. 2.22.1 and 2.34.2.

³⁶ This is true despite the fact that this type of shield was common also among Italic peoples, the Romans included, and in the Hellenistic armies of the Near East, as well as among other barbarians: for an exhaustive discussion see P.F. Stary, 'Ursprung und Ausbreitung der eisenzeitlichen Ovalschilde mit spindelförmigem Schildbuckel', *Germania* 59 (1981), pp. 287–306, and M. Eichberg, *Scutum. Die Entwicklung einer italisch-etruskischen Schildform von den Anfängen bis zur Zeit Caesars* (Frankfurt am Main etc., 1987). For the representations of oblong shields as attributes of the Gauls, see e.g. P. Bieńkowski, *Die Darstellungen der Gallier in der hellenistischen Kunst* (Vienna, 1908); P. Bieńkowski, *Les Celtes dans les arts mineurs greco-romains* (Cracow, 1928); G. Colonna, 'Celti e celtomachie nell'arte etrusca', in: D. Poli (ed.), *La battaglia del Sentino. Scontro fra nazioni e incontro in una nazione. Atti del convegno di studi Camerino-Sassoferrato 1998* (Rome, 2002), pp. 163–87.

perhaps in reference to the Gauls, already on *aes signatum*.³⁷ On Roman denarii, it is shown crossed with a *carnyx* as a moneyer's mark as early as the end of the third century (*RRC* 128/1). Subsequent occurrences of the Gallic oval shield obviously are too numerous to list in the present context, but it is worth recalling that the best-known numismatic depictions are related to Caesar's conquest of Gaul: it appears on Saserna's famous 'Vercingetorix'-denarii (*RRC* 448/2), both on the obverse, behind the head of the Celt sometimes identified as the Arvernian chieftain,³⁸ and on the reverse, in the hand of the Gallic warrior fighting from the chariot. On the denarius type of Albinus mentioned above (*RRC* 450/1), an oval shield is to be seen in the upper field between two crossed *carnyces* on the reverse. Furthermore, such a shield appears, for instance, among the spoils of (an apparently Gallic) victory proudly exhibited by M. Aemilius Lepidus (cos. 187) on *RRC* 419/1.³⁹ Also, it is depicted on reverses of denarii of the Caesarian moneyer A. Licinius Nerva (*RRC* 454/1–2, 47 BC): the bearded barbarian beneath the Roman rider clearly is a Celt,⁴⁰ and on at least one reverse die not only the central umbo, but also the rib of his shield are visible.⁴¹

The ornamentation of the oblong shield on our denarii of Calvus is misdescribed by Crawford as a "thunderbolt".⁴² As already pointed out by Hollstein, the four S-shaped elements which are in evidence here are also depicted on the shield of the Gallic *tropaemum* on Caesar's denarii *RRC* 452/1–2.⁴³ They are doubtless meant to render, in a schematic way, the rich decoration of Gallic shields;⁴⁴ the design does not, however, resemble a thunderbolt.

It goes without saying that oval shields are a constant element of so-called Gallic trophies on Roman Republican coins from around 100 BC onwards,⁴⁵ together with the *carnyx*, spear (or perhaps rather javelin; sometimes a pair of them) and horned

³⁷ *RRC* 7/1, first half of third cent. BC. Typologically, the object on these bars is to be compared to the oval shield of a Gallic warrior on the bronzes struck at the Latin colony of Ariminum (*HN Italy* 8: 268–25 BC). Regarding the interpretation of the shield on the *aes signatum* *RRC* 7/1, cf. *RRC* 9/1, where an elephant is depicted: war elephants were used by Rome's enemies in the Pyrrhic and First Punic Wars.

³⁸ On this type, see Woytek, 'Der Fremde im Münzbild' (n. 29 above), 109.

³⁹ For a discussion of the iconography of this coin type see A. Zawadzka, 'Gallic horned helmets on Roman Republican coins', *Archeologia* 60 (2009), pp. 35–43, at 39f., with the illustration on pl. III, no. 3. For an example of *RRC* 419/1e, on which the horned helmets are clearly in evidence, see also R. Russo and A. de Falco, *The RBW Collection of Roman Republican Coins* (Zurich – London, 2013), no. 1510.

⁴⁰ See J.-L. Desnier, 'Le Gaulois dans l'imaginaire monétaire de la République romaine. Images plurielles d'une réalité singulière', *MEFRA* 103 (1991), pp. 605–54, at pp. 646–7, as well as Woytek, 'Der Fremde im Münzbild' (n. 29 above), p. 110.

⁴¹ See Peus 366 (29 Oct. 2000), no. 1225 (3.82g), struck from the same dies as CNG Mail Bid Sale 79 (17 Sept. 2008), no. 994 (3.72g).

⁴² *RRC*, p. 457.

⁴³ Hollstein, *Die stadtrömische Münzprägung* (n. 5 above), p. 365.

⁴⁴ See, for example, the ornamented shields depicted on the triumphal arch of Orange: R. Amy et al., *L'arc d'Orange* (Paris, 1962), pls 16–20. For an overview of the sources for the decoration of Celtic shields, see G.-Ch. Picard and J.-J. Hatt, 'Panneaux d'armes et trophées', in: R. Amy et al., *L'arc d'Orange*, pp. 77–88, at 82–4.

⁴⁵ See the issues commemorating Marius' victories over the Cimbri and Teutones (reverses of *RRC* 326/2 etc.), as well as Caesar's conquest of Gaul.

helmet.⁴⁶ Hence, the iconography of the Gallic trophy on our type D may be regarded as entirely conventional.⁴⁷

The standard in the form of a boar (on our type B) is a different matter. The denarii of Coelius Caldus, RRC 437/2–3, feature the only depiction of this object in the whole of Roman Republican coinage. Hence, it is necessary to turn to evidence from other media and other periods in order to contextualise the image. The boar standard's presence and importance in the Celtic milieu in general is attested by archaeological finds, as well as by its depiction on Celtic coinage.⁴⁸ Also, there are several representations of such standards on Roman weapon friezes, e.g. on the Arch of Orange (dating to the early Julio-Claudian period).⁴⁹ Furthermore, a man carrying a boar standard is depicted on the skirt flaps of an Augustan cuirass statue fragment in Copenhagen.⁵⁰ Most importantly, for our purpose, a boar standard appears several times in association with a personification of Gallia, in the Roman documentation. The most famous attestation is to be found on the cuirass of the Prima Porta statue of Augustus, where *Gallia devicta* is shown on the viewer's right hand side, in the guise of a captive woman sitting to the left, with a *carnyx* and an empty scabbard in her hands and a boar standard in front of her.⁵¹ On denarii of Galba minted in Spain, which show on their reverses Gallia and Hispania (identified as such in the legend) clasping hands, the personification of Gaul sometimes holds a sceptre surmounted by a small boar sculpture⁵² – this is doubtless a 'romanised' depiction of a boar-standard.⁵³ Further pertinent numismatic evidence is provided by the anonymous coinage presumably to be associated with C. Iulius Civilis, the Batavian leader of the revolt against the Romans in Germania inferior and Gaul in AD 69–70. Here

⁴⁶ See the discussion and enlarged illustrations in Zawadzka (n. 39 above), plate II. A torque and mail coat are depicted only occasionally: see especially RRC 468/2. Sometimes Gallic captives are placed at the trophy's foot; on these see Desnier, 'Le Gaulois' (n. 40 above), at pp. 608–14.

⁴⁷ Its long sword, contrasted with a short sword of the other trophy, also points to the Gallic context: for a general introduction to Gallic weaponry and armour, see J.-L. Brunaux and B. Lambot, *Guerre et armement chez les Gaulois, 450–52 av. J.-C.* (Paris, 1987). For their representations on Roman coins, see P. Couissin, 'L'équipement de guerre des Gaulois sur les monnaies romaines', *RN (4^e série)* 31 (1928), pp. 28–55 and 161–86.

⁴⁸ See J. Moreau, 'Les enseignes militaires dans le monde celtique et leurs figurations antiques', in: J. Moreau, D. Ankner, R. Boudet et al., *Le sanglier-enseigne gaulois de Soulac-sur-Mer (Gironde). Étude de l'emblématique du sanglier dans le monde celtique* (Soulac-sur-Mer, 1995), pp. 20–7; also M. Dhénin, 'Le sanglier-enseigne dans la numismatique gauloise', *ibid.*, pp. 28–42. For a selection of numismatic comparanda see also S. Hurter, 'Ein unbekannter keltischer Viertelstater aus Nordfrankreich', *SM* 43, issue 169 (1993), pp. 8–10.

⁴⁹ See R. Amy et al., *L'arc d'Orange* (n. 44 above), pls 16–20.

⁵⁰ Ny Carlsberg Glyptothek, inv. 554a. See Bieńkowski, *Les Celtes* (n. 36 above), p. 60, fig. 109; A.L. Kuttner, *Dynasty and Empire in the Age of Augustus. The Case of the Boscoreale Cups* (Berkeley – Los Angeles – Oxford, 1995), fig. 82.

⁵¹ P. Bieńkowski, *De simulacris barbararum gentium apud Romanos* (Cracoviae, 1900), pp. 28f., fig. 3; E. Simon, *Augustus. Kunst und Leben in Rom um die Zeitenwende* (Munich, 1986), pp. 53f., fig. 56; Kuttner, *Dynasty and Empire* (n. 50 above), fig. 64d. The empty scabbard has been interpreted as referring to the fact that Gaul had already been subdued and 'disarmed' by Julius Caesar, before the principate of Augustus.

⁵² This detail is in evidence on a specimen of RIC I² Galba 18 at the British Museum: *BMCRE* Galba 170 (reg. no. R.10132); see also Sutherland's note to RIC Galba 15 on p. 233.

⁵³ Thus Dhénin, 'Le sanglier-enseigne' (n. 48 above), p. 40.

the boar standard appears twice. First, on denarii with the right-facing bust of the personification of GALLIA on the obverse: their reverse shows clasped hands holding two corn-ears and a boar standard.⁵⁴ The reverse legend FIDES seems to indicate that these coins alluded to the loyalty of Civilis' Gallic allies around Iulius Classicus. The denarius of the same group with the bust of LIBERTAS RESTITVTA on the obverse points in the same direction, iconographically: its reverse shows CONCORDIA, holding a *caduceus* in her left hand and a boar standard in the right.⁵⁵ In any case, it is clear from the material assembled here that the boar standard on the denarii of Coelius Calvus must be a symbol of his ancestor's military success against the Gauls.⁵⁶

On types B and C, the various symbols standing for Calvus' Gallic victory – the *carynx*, spear and boar standard – are juxtaposed with an object that unquestionably symbolises a Spanish victory, namely a “standard inscribed HIS”, in Crawford's words.⁵⁷ The way in which the object should refer to this success is not immediately obvious. The combination with the Celtic boar standard on type B of course *prima facie* suggests that this might be a local, barbarian military standard from Spain.⁵⁸ But, in fact, the object looks exactly like a well-known kind of military standard used in the Roman army: a *vexillum*, which has the form of a rectangular (or square) flag with fringes at its lower end, hanging on a horizontal cross-bar attached to a shaft.⁵⁹ However, the *vexillum* was not only a tactical standard in the Roman army, but also a special military decoration, awarded initially only to commanders-in-chief and later, during the imperial period, reserved for high-ranking officers.⁶⁰ From the one certain representation of the *vexillum* as a military decoration, it is possible to infer that it was an exact replica of normal Roman military *vexilla*.⁶¹ In view of the fact that the *vexillum* awarded to Agrippa after one of his major naval victories was

⁵⁴ RIC I² Civil Wars 131.

⁵⁵ RIC I² Civil Wars 132.

⁵⁶ It definitely should not be taken to convey any specific association with Celtiberia – something that Badian did not wish to exclude: ‘Two numismatic phantoms’ (n. 15 above), p. 48.

⁵⁷ RRC, p. 458. Similarly Hollstein, *Die stadtrömische Münzprägung* (n. 5 above), p. 365: “mit HIS(*pania*) beschriebene Standarte”.

⁵⁸ This is the approach taken by numismatists of the early modern period: see the quotations in the *Thesaurus Morellianus, sive familiarum Romanarum numismata omnia, diligentissime undique conquisita, ad ipsorum nummorum fidem accuratissime delineata, & juxta ordinem Fulvii Ursini & Caroli Patini disposita, a celeberrimo antiquario Andrea Morellio. [...] Nunc primum edidit & Commentario perpetuo illustravit Sigebertus Havercampus*, 2 vols (Amsterdam, 1734), p. 103 (citing Perizonius and Morell).

⁵⁹ On the one linen flag of a *vexillum* that has come down to us from the Roman period (dimensions: 47x50 cm), see M. Rostovtzeff, ‘*Vexillum* and victory’, *JRS* 32 (1942), pp. 92–106, as well as Th. Fischer, *Die Armee der Caesaren. Archäologie und Geschichte. Mit Beiträgen von Ronald Bockius, Dietrich Boschung, Thomas Schmidts* (Regensburg, 2012), pp. 232f. (with colour photograph).

⁶⁰ On the *vexillum* as a *donum militare* in general, see P. Steiner, *Die dona militaria* (Bonn, 1905; also published in *Bonner Jahrbücher* 114/115 [1906]), pp. 29–31, as well as V.A. Maxfield, *The Military Decorations of the Roman Army* (Berkeley – Los Angeles, 1981), pp. 82–4. It must have been introduced after Polybius' time (since he does not mention it in his list of awards), but before Sallustius (see bell. Iug. 85.29, where Marius claims to have been awarded a *vexillum*); for the fact that it was reserved for high officers in the imperial period, see Steiner, p. 89.

⁶¹ CIL III 454 = ILS 2663. See Maxfield, *Military Decorations* (n. 60 above), plate 5b. The monument dates from the Trajanic period.

blue,⁶² it seems logical to assume that the design of honorary *vexilla* was adapted to the particular victory which the recipient had achieved. The moneyer's ancestor may have been presented with such an award for his campaigns in Spain, and in this case the *vexillum*'s inscription HIS would be easy to explain. Since military decorations were probably displayed in the *atrium* of the house of the recipient, and kept there after his death,⁶³ a depiction on the denarii of his descendant would make good sense. If this explanation is correct, the coins RRC 437/2–4 would feature the earliest depiction of a *vexillum* as a military decoration.⁶⁴

From the above discussion it is evident that the obverse types B and C have a parallel structure: on each of them, a symbol denoting a Hispanic victory is coupled with one symbol (boar standard) or a set of two symbols (*carnyx* and spear) referring to the victory over the Salluvii. Types A and D also feature a dual structure, with two symbols in the field or two depictions to the left and right of the 'altar', one of which clearly refers to Gaul in each case. Thus, Ockham's razor makes it necessary to take a close look at the non-Gallic depictions in these cases. The two current standard numismatic treatments of the issue of Caldus (RRC 437), by Crawford and Hollstein, interpret these corresponding images (the round shield and trophy with round shield respectively) as referring to "an otherwise unattested military success in the East".⁶⁵ Ockham's razor prompts the question: can they possibly denote the Hispanic victory as well, like the *vexillum* with HIS?

Briefly, the answer is yes. The decisive iconographic element in this respect is the round shield on types A and D. The shield has a central umbo and additional decorations in the form of several dots near the edge, and semicircles, although, on the various dies, the rendering of the shield's decoration is of course not always consistent. It is true that this design is somewhat reminiscent of the classic appearance of the so-called Macedonian shield,⁶⁶ which is why Crawford and Hollstein regarded the round shield as such and hypothesised that, apart from successes against Gauls and Spaniards, the coins RRC 437 also commemorated a Macedonian victory.

However, round shields with a central umbo and additional decorations in the form of dots and lines are not automatically to be identified as Macedonian. Wilhelm Hollstein recently published a convincing re-interpretation of Julius Caesar's quinarii RRC 452/3,⁶⁷ in which he demonstrated that the reverse of these coins, struck in 48 BC, in fact shows a Spanish trophy (not a Gallic one). It refers back to Caesar's military successes in Hispania ulterior as a propraetor in 61/60 BC – an interpretation already given by Haverkamp in the 18th century, but forgotten since.⁶⁸ The main

⁶² Suet. Aug. 25.3; according to Cassius Dio (51.23.3), Agrippa was awarded the *vexillum* only after the conquest of Egypt.

⁶³ Steiner, *dona militaria* (n. 60), p. 92.

⁶⁴ An article on the *vexillum* in the numismatic evidence by Anna Zawadzka is currently in preparation.

⁶⁵ RRC, p. 459; Hollstein, *Die stadtrömische Münzprägung* (n. 5 above), pp. 366f.

⁶⁶ On which see K. Liampi, *Der makedonische Schild* (Bonn, 1998); in this monograph, the denarii of Caldus are listed as featuring Macedonian shields (p. 162, M 137–8), since for the Republican material Liampi based her work on RRC.

⁶⁷ W. Hollstein, 'Caesars spanische Statthalterschaft im Münzbild', in: R. Lehmann, B. Hamborg, A. V. Siebert et al. (eds), *Nub Nefer – Gutes Gold. Gedenkschrift für Manfred Gutgesell* (Rahden/Westf., 2014), pp. 151–7.

⁶⁸ *Thesaurus Morellianus* (n. 58 above), p. 208.

elements of Caesar's trophy are a short sword and a round shield with a central umbo, decorated with dots.⁶⁹

That the round shield was one of the most characteristic Spanish weapons, in Roman eyes, is best seen on various precious metal issues of the emperors Galba and Vespasian minted in Spain, on which the personification of the peninsula, identified as HISPANIA in the legend, is depicted with a round shield and two javelins.⁷⁰ On denarii struck in Spain by Cn. Pompeius jr., more than one hundred years earlier (*RRC* 469), the same personification appears with the same attributes.⁷¹ Roman sources call these Spanish shields *caetrae*,⁷² and Hispanic soldiers or (auxiliary) troops are often referred to as *caetrati* in them.⁷³ The presence of round shields of the *caetra* type is also well attested in the Spanish archaeological record and in indigenous iconography.⁷⁴

In his recent article cited above, Hollstein gathered and discussed further Roman issues, Republican and Augustan, on which a round shield is represented as a symbol of victory over Spanish peoples. For example, the *caetra* appears, together with a short sword, encircled by a laurel wreath, on the reverses of denarii struck by M. Pupius Piso, where it refers to the Hispanic campaigns of the moneyer's father, proconsul in Hispania ulterior in 71–69 BC, and his Spanish triumph in 69.⁷⁵ *Caetrae* feature most prominently on various types of the interesting silver coinage struck in 25–3 BC in Emerita by the *legatus Augusti pro praetore* P. Carisius, who had successfully campaigned against the Asturians. One round shield adorns a *tropaeum* with two javelins, which is placed on the triangular heap of similar *caetrae* and other Hispanic spoils of war. On other types of Carisius, the round shield is part of a *tropaeum* being crowned by Victory, or it is featured as the main design of the reverse, flanked by

⁶⁹On the basis of this image, Hollstein argued that on the denarii of the moneyer D. Iunius Albinus, *RRC* 450/1, also struck in 48 BC, the round shield inserted among Gallic attributes (two *carnyces* and an oblong shield) should also be interpreted as referring to Spain – and commemorating not only Caesar's Hispanic victories, but also those of the moneyer's grandfather: see Hollstein, 'Caesars spanische Statthalterschaft' (n. 67 above), pp. 154f.

⁷⁰*RIC* I² Galba 1–3, 15–21; *RIC* II.1² Vespasian 1295–6.

⁷¹Compare also the round shields in evidence on several varieties of the Spanish denarii of M. Minatius Sabinus (*RRC* 470/1a: below the feet of the personification; 1b: in the hands of the kneeling personification; 1c–d: on the trophy shouldered by one personification).

⁷²Varro *Men.* frg. 88 Buecheler = Astbury: *quis rutundam facere cetram nequeat?*; Serv. *Aen.* 7.732: *caetra est scutum loreum, quo utuntur Afri et Hispani*; cf. Liv. 21.27.5, Luc. 7.232; Sil. 3.348 and 10.230.

⁷³E.g. Liv. 21.21.12, 23.26.11; Sil. 9.231; see also Caes. *civ.* 1.39.1, 48.7 (*caetrati citerioris Hispaniae*), 55.1, 70.4–5, 75.2 (on the local forces mobilised by Afranius and Petreius).

⁷⁴On the *caetra* and other elements of Spanish military equipment, see F. Quesada Sanz, *El armamento ibérico. Estudio tipológico, geográfico, funcional, social y simbólico de las armas en la cultura ibérica (siglos VI–I a.C.)*. Monographies Instrumentum 3.1–2, 2 vols (Montagnac, 1997); E. Peralta Labrador, *Los Cántabros antes de Roma*. Bibliotheca Archaeologica Hispana 5 (2nd ed. Madrid, 2003), pp. 188–211. For representations of Spanish weapons on indigenous coins, see F. Quesada Sanz, 'Ibers, monedes i armes', in: M. Campo (ed.), *Els Ibers, cultura y moneda* (exhibition catalogue Barcelona, 2009), pp. 78–83.

⁷⁵*RRC* 418/1–2, reverses; misdescribed by Crawford: see Hollstein, *Die stadtrömische Münzprägung* (n. 5 above), pp. 219–21.

a curved sword and a spearhead.⁷⁶ On the latter pieces, the *caetra* is decorated with a central umbo and an octagonal decoration with dots.⁷⁷ One of the most powerful reverse images of the Carisius group shows a bearded, nude captive kneeling to the right, with his hands tied behind his back, beneath a trophy comprising a *caetra*, among other equipment (**pl. 19, fig. 7**).⁷⁸

The similarity of the composition of this early Augustan image to the reverses of denarii of the moneyer C. Memmius (*RRC* 427/1: **pl. 19, fig. 8**) is striking. On these coins, too, a nude male captive is kneeling to the right under a trophy featuring a round shield (as well as a helmet, sword and also two crossed javelins); this reverse is invariably accompanied by the legend C. MEMMIVS IMPERATOR. In the past, the reverse type of these coins, struck c. 57/6 BC,⁷⁹ gave rise to speculations over unattested victories of a moneyer's relative in Macedonia or Asia minor,⁸⁰ but the recent discovery of a Roman Republican inscription in the province of Cádiz in southern Spain has made these conjectures obsolete: the stone reads C. MEMMIO [...] IMPERATOR[I] and confirms the impression one gets from looking at these coins, viz. that an ancestor of the moneyer Memmius may have been acclaimed for a Spanish victory.⁸¹

The Spanish trophy on the issue of Memmius, which was produced at the mint of Rome just a few years before the denarii of Coelius Caldus, is extremely similar to the non-Gallic trophy on the reverse of *RRC* 437/2–4 (our type D): just like the trophy of Caldus it comprises a helmet, a round shield, a sword and two crossed javelins – as we saw above, two javelins are often combined with a *caetra* in the hands of the personification of Hispania. Moreover, even the decoration of the shield on the denarii of Memmius corresponds precisely to the decoration of the round shields on Caldus' coins, in many cases: a central umbo and dots within semicircles.

The application of Ockham's razor leaves no doubt: the round shield and the trophy comprising a round shield on types A and D of *RRC* 437 must not be taken as starting points for a hypothetical reconstruction of unattested eastern campaigns and victories of one of the moneyer's ancestors, but they clearly refer to the Spanish victory also alluded to by the *vexillum* inscribed HIS on other coin types of Caldus.

⁷⁶ *RIC* I² Augustus 4–5, 1, 2–3.

⁷⁷ Denarii signed by Octavian himself (IMP CAE–SAR DIVI F: *RIC* I² Augustus 543) feature a comparable round shield on its own, decorated with three concentric dotted circles around the umbo. These coins would also seem to refer to Spain, although their precise chronology and mint attribution is uncertain.

⁷⁸ *RIC* I² Augustus 6.

⁷⁹ Hollstein, *Die stadtrömische Münzprägung* (n. 5 above), p. 381.

⁸⁰ Crawford, *RRC* p. 451; Hollstein, *Die stadtrömische Münzprägung* (n. 5 above), pp. 297f.

⁸¹ See the publication by J. González, 'C. MEMMIVS IMPERATOR', *HABIS* 24 (1993), 281–6, and especially B. Díaz Ariño, 'C. Memmius, gobernador de la Hispania Ulterior', *ZPE* 157 (2006), pp. 231–6, who convincingly identifies the *imperator* with the moneyer's grandfather (tr. pl. 111; killed in 100 BC, when he was running for consul: *MRR* 1, p. 574; cf. F. Münzer, article 'Memmius no. 5', *RE* 15.1 [1931], cols 604–7), who seems to have governed Hispania ulterior in 103/102 BC.

A similar conclusion was already hinted at by Picard,⁸² and more recently by Harlan,⁸³ who did not, however, proceed to a structural analysis of the issue's iconography as a whole. In fact, by tabulating our interpretations of the various iconographical elements it becomes evident that the design of these denarii was clearly structured (see *Table 1*). On each type, there are references to both Spain and Gaul; while on *RRC 437/1* these references are confined to the reverse, they occur on both obverse and reverse of all the other types. Hence, the coin types may be seen to be perfectly balanced, from an iconographic point of view.

Varieties of <i>RRC 437</i>	Our illustrations	Reference to Spain	Reference to Gaul
1a–b	Fig. 1	rev.: round shield	rev.: oblong shield
2a–b, 3a–b	Figs 2–3	obv.: <i>vexillum</i> inscribed HIS rev.: trophy with round shield etc.	obv.: boar standard rev.: trophy with <i>cornyx</i> etc.
4a–b	Fig. 4–5	obv.: <i>vexillum</i> inscribed HIS rev.: trophy with round shield etc.	obv. <i>cornyx</i> and spear rev.: trophy with <i>cornyx</i> etc.

Table 1: A synopsis of the iconographic references to Spain and Gaul on the denarii of CALDVS III VIR

The reverse legend of *RRC 437/2–4* and prosopographical problems

Ernst Badian's main contribution to the study of the issue of Calvus consists in his trenchant critique of the interpretation of the legend of the reverse type featuring the *VIIvir epulonum* and the two trophies, viz. C. CALDVS – IMP A (or AV/AN) X. He demonstrated that the expansion “*imperator, augur, decemvir (sacris faciundis)*”, continuously passed on in scholarship from at least as early as Mommsen (1860)⁸⁴ to Sydenham (1952),⁸⁵ Crawford (1974), Hollstein (1993)⁸⁶ and Harlan (1995),⁸⁷ must be wrong: “no one, with the exception of men who seized control of the *res publica* [...] is known to have held two of the highest priesthoods at any time after the Second Punic War”; “a *novus homo* ought never to have been credited with these two priesthoods”;⁸⁸ “no Roman of the late Republic [...] would have read A as Augur and X as Decemvir”; “A.X can only be read as A(nnis/os) (decem)”;⁸⁹ “any contemporary Roman would have read the message of these coins as referring to a C. Calvus who

⁸² G.C. Picard, *Les trophées romains. Contribution à l'histoire de la Religion et de l'Art triomphal de Rome*. BEFAR 187 (Paris, 1957), p. 135, n. 3: “Les trophées se rapportent aux victoires de C. Calvus, grand-père du monétaire [...] en Espagne ultérieure. [...] Les armes qui les composent sont ibériques (rondache) ou galatiques.”

⁸³ Harlan, *Roman Republican Moneyers* (n. 11 above), p. 164, followed by Badian, ‘Two numismatic phantoms’ (n. 15 above), pp. 54f.

⁸⁴ Th. Mommsen, *Geschichte des römischen Münzwesens* (Berlin, 1860), p. 637.

⁸⁵ E.A. Sydenham, *The Coinage of the Roman Republic* (London, 1952), p. 148, no. 894.

⁸⁶ Although these two scholars adopted the interpretation with some misgivings: see *RRC*, p. 459, and Hollstein, *Die stadtrömische Münzprägung* (n. 5 above), p. 366.

⁸⁷ Harlan, *Roman Republican Moneyers* (n. 11 above), p. 165.

⁸⁸ Badian, ‘Two numismatic phantoms’ (n. 15 above), p. 53.

⁸⁹ Badian, ‘Two numismatic phantoms’ (n. 15 above), p. 56.

was emperor for ten years”.⁹⁰ Badian’s interpretation met with criticism from Frank Ryan, but the alternative which Ryan proposed in a paper dedicated exclusively to the problem of the legend is not attractive. He preferred the expansion IMP(*erio*) AV(*spicioque*) X (= *decies*), taking the inscription as a claim that C. Calvus was “ten times victorious as a supreme commander”.⁹¹ While it is true that *imperio auspicioque* is a set phrase, it is normally not used in combination with numerals, counting single victories in battle. Furthermore, it is highly questionable that contemporary coin users could have understood the abbreviation X as meaning “ten battles”. Ryan’s interpretation is more complex, and clearly much more problematic than Badian’s, which is why we adopt the latter.

With the help of Badian’s interpretation of the legend and our explanation of the military imagery, it is possible to settle another major question that has been associated with these coins for centuries: how many Coelii Caldi figure on the denarii RRC 437, either through their depiction or through references to their activity? The minimum is three, but repeatedly scholars have made a case for four; let us quote Bartolomeo Borghesi: “È evidente che quattro sono i soggetti qui ricordati, cioè il triumviro Caldo che fece coniare la moneta, Lucio Caldo settemviro epulone a cui spetta il lettisternio, Cajo Caldo imperatore cui appartengono i trofei, finalmente il console Cajo Celio Caldo”.⁹² In the same vein, Götz Lahusen and R.J. Evans proposed to ascribe the military victories commemorated by the trophies not to the consul Calvus portrayed on the obverse of these coins, but to a hypothetical uncle of the moneyer.⁹³ As Badian fittingly pointed out, if his expansion of the reverse legend to “*imperator annos decem*” is correct, the inscription is bound to refer to the *homo novus* depicted on the obverse of the coins, the best-known member of the family: in the generation after him, much better documented prosopographically, “no one could have been *imperator* for ten years (i.e. until the mid-sixties) and escape all literary notice”.⁹⁴ Consequently, only three Coelii Caldi are featured on the coins.⁹⁵

The career of C. Coelius Calvus, the consul of 94 BC, cannot be fully reconstructed. The one literary testimony to his activity in the provinces is the sentence in Liv. per. 73, already cited above (*C. Coelius in Gallia transalpina Salluvios rebellantes vicit*; 90 BC). For his military activities in Spain, our coins are the only direct source. He must have been praetor in 100 or 99 BC,⁹⁶ and it has been suggested that he went

⁹⁰ Badian, ‘Two numismatic phantoms’ (n. 15 above), p. 57.

⁹¹ F. Ryan, ‘Die Legende IMP.AV.X auf den Denaren des Triumvirn Calvus’, *SM* 56, issue 222 (2006), pp. 39–42, p. 42: “C. Calvus hat als Oberbefehlshaber (IMP[*erio*] AV[*spicioque*]) in Iberien und Gallien insgesamt zehn Male (X = *decies*) den Sieg errungen.”

⁹² Borghesi, *Œuvres numismatiques* (n. 2 above), vol. 1, p. 321.

⁹³ R.J. Evans, ‘The denarius issue of CALDVVS IIIVIR and associated problems’, *The Ancient History Bulletin* 5, nos 5–6 (1991), pp. 129–34; Lahusen, *Bildnismünzen* (n. 7 above), p. 20. For arguments against Lahusen’s reconstruction, see Hollstein, *Die stadtrömische Münzprägung* (n. 5 above), p. 368, n. 35.

⁹⁴ Badian, ‘Two numismatic phantoms’ (n. 15 above), p. 57.

⁹⁵ As correctly seen already by Picard, *Les trophées* (n. 82 above), p. 135, n. 3: “il n’y a pas de raison d’inventer un C. Calvus inconnu, qui aurait été proclamé *imperator* en Orient”.

⁹⁶ *MRR* 2, pp. 1 and 3, n. 2.

to Spain after his praetorship, i.e. from 99/98 BC.⁹⁷ Julius Obsequens happens to record Roman military victories in Spain for 100 BC (*Lusitanis devictis Hispania ulterior pacata*: Obs. 44a), 99 BC (*Lusitani rebellantes subacti*: Obs. 46) and 98 BC (*Hispani pluribus proeliis devicti*: Obs. 47). The first two entries are clearly to be connected with the triumph of L. Cornelius Dolabella (pr. 100 BC?) *ex Hispania ulteriore de Lusitanis* on 26 January, 98 BC; the third might theoretically be taken to refer to Calvus – but there is another option. On the basis of his interpretation of the legend, Badian considered the possibility that C. Coelius had been sent to assume his command in Gaul already in 94 BC, the year of his consulship, and that he may have held a combined command over Gallia transalpina and Hispania citerior for such a long time that his grandson, on his denarii, could make a claim that he was a commander in the provincial area for (almost) ten years, from 94 to 86 or 85 BC: for in 85 BC C. Valerius Flaccus was proconsul in Gaul.⁹⁸ Of course one must add that Badian's interpretation of the legend most probably implies a translation of *imperator* in the original sense of the word, as “commanding an army, as a holder of *imperium*”.⁹⁹ Calvus did receive an imperatorial acclamation, but this was probably only a few years into his tenure – it is plausible to assume that he was acclaimed for his victory over the Salluvii in 90 BC, the only one that made it into the literary record, although this dating is, in our opinion, unprovable.¹⁰⁰ In conclusion, it has to be stressed that, regarding the reconstruction of the career of C. Coelius Calvus, cos. 94 BC, we are in the realm of speculation, and will probably continue to be so until new evidence becomes available.

The head of Sol

Our interpretation of the types and symbols referring to military victories on *RRC* 437 has a direct bearing on the understanding of the head of Sol on 437/1. Crawford proposed to view the head in connection with what he took to be a Macedonian shield, and postulated a reference to an otherwise unattested victory in the East,¹⁰¹ Hollstein preferred to associate it with some mysterious exploit in the “Orient jenseits der Ägäis”.¹⁰² More recently, Frank Ryan proposed to maintain a geographical interpretation of the head of Sol, but surprisingly opted for an association with the West: “Wir wissen, dass C. Coelius Calvus in bzw. nach seiner Prätur Statthalter einer der spanischen Provinzen war. Es ist durchaus möglich, dass der Solkopf eben diese Statthalterschaft feiert. Die Sonne bleibt ja nicht den ganzen Tag über im Osten, dort

⁹⁷ See *MRR* 2, p. 5.

⁹⁸ *MRR* 2, pp. 58–60, and 3, p. 211. Badian, ‘Two numismatic phantoms’ (n. 15 above), pp. 57–60.

⁹⁹ That is, in the sense explained in detail by Cicero, *de oratore* 1.210. See D. Kienast, ‘Imperator’, *Zeitschrift der Savigny-Stiftung für Rechtsgeschichte, Romanistische Abteilung* 78 (1961), pp. 403–21, pp. 404f.

¹⁰⁰ Badian, ‘Two numismatic phantoms’ (n. 15 above), pp. 50, 57 and 60, accepted Crawford's argument that Calvus was acclaimed for his victory against the Salluvii, since the CALDVVS IMP in the reverse inscription always stands next to the Gallic trophy, but, as explained above, this point does not seem unassailable.

¹⁰¹ *RRC*, p. 459.

¹⁰² Hollstein, *Die stadtrömische Münzprägung* (n. 5 above), p. 367.

geht sie lediglich auf. Im Westen aber geht sie unter, weswegen sie in literarischen Quellen auch mit dem Land der Hesperiden verbunden wird.” He then went on to hypothesise, on the basis of this image, that C. Coelius Caldus governed Hispania ulterior, the westernmost province of the Roman Empire.¹⁰³

This is not convincing. As was recognised by Harlan, the head of Sol, in all probability, does not have any geographical connotation at all on these coins.¹⁰⁴ However, the alternative explanation advanced by him – viz. that the Coelii Caldi claimed descent from the god Sol and the moneyer therefore pictured a bust of his divine ancestor – hardly seems credible either.¹⁰⁵ One is well-advised to return to the interpretation of the type given in early modern numismatic literature, where the head of Sol was taken to be a pun on the moneyer’s name. Over three centuries ago Jean Vaillant explained that “the radiate head of Sol refers to the gentile name Coelius and the cognomen Caldus, because the sun is to be seen in the sky [lat. *caelum/coelum*], and it is hot [lat. *caldus*].”¹⁰⁶ Since we know from Cicero that the cognomen of this branch of the family could also be interpreted in a negative way,¹⁰⁷ it may have made sense to publicise the family’s preferred reading.

The interpretation of the coin-type as a pun on the family name was endorsed by Joseph Eckhel,¹⁰⁸ who also adduced a passage from Varro’s *de re rustica* in its support, where the phrase “*sol caldus*” is attested.¹⁰⁹ As is well known, puns of this kind occur not infrequently in the late Republican and Augustan denarius coinage.¹¹⁰

The *epulum*

Crawford was unambiguous: “There is no connection between the *epulum* and the trophies”.¹¹¹ In view of the iconographic composition of the reverse type of RRC 437/2–4, this a priori seems surprising: the trophies are obviously part of the main image of this side of the denarii, and not secondary types or symbols merely

¹⁰³ F. Ryan, ‘Der Sonnengott auf den Münzen der römischen Republik’, *RSN* 84 (2005), pp. 81–92, p. 84.

¹⁰⁴ Harlan, *Roman Republican Moneyers* (n. 11 above), p. 165.

¹⁰⁵ Thus already Badian, ‘Two numismatic phantoms’ (n. 15 above), p. 55.

¹⁰⁶ J. Vaillant, *Nummi antiqui familiarum Romanarum perpetuis interpretationibus illustrati*, 2 vols (Amsterdam, 1703), vol. 1, p. 292: “caput Solis radiatum, adludens Coelio nomini & cognomini Caldo, quod Sol in coelo videatur, & caldus sit”. The idea goes back to the humanist Stephanus Winandus Pighius (1520–1604): see I. Eckhel, *Doctrina numorum veterum*, vol. 5 (*continens numos consulares et familiarum*) (Vienna, 1795), p. 176.

¹⁰⁷ Cic. *de inventione* 2.28: the name Caldus could be taken as betraying a reckless and desultory state of mind.

¹⁰⁸ Eckhel, *Doctrina* (n. 106 above), p. 176: “[Pighius] in hoc typo usitatam ad nomen adlusionem videt; nam sive *Coelum* [sic; apparently a misprint for: *Coelium*] respicias, sol per *coelum* gyrat, sive *Caldum*, sol *calorem* efficit”.

¹⁰⁹ Varro, *de re rustica* 3.2.1: *Comitiis aediliciis cum sole caldo ego et Q. Axius senator tribulis suffragium tulissemus...*

¹¹⁰ See RRC 316/1 (Thorius Balbus: bull), 317/2–3 (Saturninus: Saturn), 337/1 (Silanus: Silenus), 410 (Pomponius Musa: the nine Muses), 526 (Voconius Vitulus: calf); *RIC* I² Augustus 308–9 (Aquilus Florus: flower).

¹¹¹ RRC, p. 459, n. 3. Hollstein, *Die stadtrömische Münzprägung* (n. 5 above), p. 369 followed him on this point.

accompanying the main type. They stand very close to the ‘altar’ on which the ritual meal is being prepared, literally flanking it, on the same exergual line. Doubts whether the dissociation of the trophies from the centrally depicted scene can be correct become even stronger when one considers the context of *epula* in Republican Rome. *Lectisternia* were closely connected to – and sometimes combined with – *supplicationes*, religious solemnities (or days of prayer) observed by the entire *populus Romanus*, by order of the consuls or the senate.¹¹² These festivities took place *circa omnia templa (pulvinaria)*.¹¹³ One of the most frequent occasions of *supplicationes* was thanksgiving for a military victory over external enemies; in the Late Republic, the aspect of the tribute to the victorious commander became ever more important.¹¹⁴ In this period, the number of days for which *supplicationes* were decreed became a measure of the significance of the victory won – and, of course, the success of the general. While *supplicationes* had originally been decreed for just one day, they lasted three, four, five, ten or even more days in the Late Republic: regarding the duration of these ceremonies, Caesar’s successes during the Gallic Wars set new standards,¹¹⁵ and Augustus boasted that during his rule, the senate had decreed *supplicationes* for victories achieved under his auspices 55 times in all, for a total of no fewer than 890 days.¹¹⁶ From a religious service, *supplicationes* had developed into a political demonstration.¹¹⁷ An imperatorial acclamation of the general victorious in the field was the essential prerequisite for *supplicationes* to be decreed, at the end of the Roman Republic.¹¹⁸ Hence, there is at least a good possibility – if not a strong likelihood – that the imperatorial acclamation of C. Coelius Caldus, a *vir consularis*, presumably for his military success against the Salluvii in 90 BC, was also followed by *supplicationes* to the gods in Rome. In view of this, it seems natural to suppose that the reverse of the denarii *RRC 437/2–4*, depicting the trophies for the

¹¹² G. Wissowa, *Religion und Kultus der Römer*. Handbuch der Klassischen Altertums-Wissenschaft V.4 (Munich, 1912), pp. 423f.: “In engem Zusammenhange mit den Lectisternien stehen die Supplicationen, d. h. die Bitt- und Dankfeste, welche auf Anordnung der Consuln bzw. des Senates vom ganzen Volke begangen werden.” See, e.g., Liv. 21.62.9, 22.10.8f.

¹¹³ G. Wissowa, article ‘Supplicationes’, *RE* 4A.1 (1931), cols 942–51, col. 944.

¹¹⁴ Wissowa, ‘Supplicationes’ (n. 113 above), cols 946f.

¹¹⁵ Caes. Gall. 2.35.4 (15 days); 4.38.5, 7.90.8 (20 days each).

¹¹⁶ *RgdA* 4.2: *Ob res a me aut per legatos meos auspiciis meis terra marique prospere gestas quinquagens et quinquens decrevit senatus supplicandum esse dis immortalibus. Dies autem, per quos ex senatus consulto supplicatum est, fuere DCCCLXXX.* On this passage, see the commentary by J. Scheid, *Res gestae divi Augusti. Hauts faits du divin Auguste* (Paris, 2007), p. 34 (with additional bibliography).

¹¹⁷ See Wissowa, *Religion und Kultus* (n. 112 above), p. 425.

¹¹⁸ See Cic. Phil. 14.11: *Etenim cui viginti his annis supplicatio decreta est, ut non imperator appellaretur aut minimis rebus gestis aut plerumque nullis?* On the specific historical and juridical situation underlying this passage, see R. Combès, *Imperator. Recherches sur l’emploi et la signification du titre d’Imperator dans la Rome républicaine*. Publications de la Faculté des Lettres et Sciences Humaines de l’Université de Montpellier 26 (Paris, 1966), pp. 76–8. On the other hand, not all the *imperatores* in whose honour *supplicationes* were decreed were also awarded a triumph, much to Cicero’s disappointment (his victory in Cilicia had earned him a *supplicatio*): see Cato in Cic. fam. 15.5.2 (*neque supplicationem sequitur semper triumphus*).

victories of Calvus next to a sacrificial scene, was intended to convey the memory of these supplications, too. Consequently, one should not interpret the elements of the reverse image, the trophies and the *epulum*, just independently from each other, but consider the reverse as a whole. Whether Calvus' son Lucius, named and depicted on the coins, really participated in the festivities on the occasion of his father's victory as *VIIvir epulonum* already, is a question of secondary importance.

Illustrations (all enlarged to 200%)

1. C. Coelius Calvus, denarius, Rome, *RRC* 437/1b: Künker 182 (14 March 2011), no. 475
2. C. Coelius Calvus, denarius, Rome, *RRC* 437/2a: NAC 72 (16 May 2013: JD), no. 1221
3. C. Coelius Calvus, denarius, Rome, *RRC* 437/2a: Peus 401 (3 November 2010), no. 441
4. C. Coelius Calvus, denarius, Rome, *RRC* 437/4a: CNG Triton 18 (6 January 2015), no. 933
5. C. Coelius Calvus, denarius, Rome, *RRC* 437/4b: American Numismatic Society, inv. 1944.100.3253
6. L. Licinius, Cn. Domitius etc., denarius serratus, Narbo, *RRC* 282/1: Gemini 8 (14 April 2011), no. 157
7. P. Carisius for Augustus, denarius, Emerita, RIC P 6: CNG Triton 11 (8 January 2008: Prideaux), no. 689
8. C. Memmius, denarius, Rome, *RRC* 427/1: NAC 63 (17 May 2012: RBW II), no. 307

PLATE 18
(All 2x)

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